

FILLET WELDS ON ASTM A36 STEEL USING AWS ERNi-1 ELECTRODE SUBJECTED TO “OUT-OF-PLANE” STRUCTURAL IMPACT LOADS

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ABSTRACT

There is a growing interest in the behavior of weldments under extreme loading conditions, such as structural impact loads. This is partly because most Codes and standards for designing welded joints are usually based on tests conducted under quasi-static or fatigue loading conditions. The primary aim of this study was to investigate the behavior of GMAW fillet welds on ASTM A36 structural steel using a high ductility electrode (AWS ERNi-1). Fillet welds were made between two sides of equal length of a very thick rectangular plate and a base plate of the same steel. Each pair of weld beads was then subjected to “out-of-plane” structural impact loads combining a relatively large moment due to bending and loads applied transversely to the fillet welds. Impact test results obtained with AWS ERNi-1 were compared with data from tests using a base metal-matching electrode, AWS ER70S-6. In this comparison, it was found that the weldments made with AWS ERNi-1 exhibited fracture initiation energy 213% higher than those made with AWS ER70S-6. Vickers hardness tests were also conducted on weld beads made with AWS ERNi-1. Comparing the hardness results before and after impact, it was found that the weld metal became up to 93% harder and the heat-affected zone up to 42% harder after impact. The fractured surfaces of the AWS ERNi-1 weld beads were analyzed and revealed characteristics typical of ductile fractures.

KEYWORDS: *Weldment under Structural Impact Load, Ductile Filler Metal (AWS ERNi-1), GMAW Fillet Welds, Nickel and Steel Filler Metals, Weld Metal Fracture Threshold*

I. INTRODUCTION

Welded structures are commonly subjected to a wide variety of loadings under different working conditions. The integrity of these structures depends on well-designed welded connections. However, engineers usually base their design of these joints on a series of Codes and standards based on quasi-static or fatigue loading. There are few studies aimed at predicting the behavior of welded structures under to dynamic structural impact loads involving high impact velocities and deformation rates. Even today, there is no consensus in these Codes and standards regarding the behavior of welded joints under structural impact loads. The ability of a structure to resist structural impacts is directly related to the energy it can absorb. However, when the structure contains welded members, its behavior is influenced by the characteristics of the welded joint in addition to the properties of the base metal [1].

Structural steels have a ferritic matrix, and their fracture behavior under impact differs significantly from that inferred from quasi-static mechanical strength tests. This behavior is influenced by various factors including temperature, strain rate, and stress concentrators, which can decrease ductility compared to standardized quasi-static tests. Like other structural components, welded joints can fail in service, often due to low ductility of the structures. Excessive rigidity in designs is more prevalent than anticipated, especially in the absence of specific standards for predicting structural behavior

under certain types or conditions of loading. Designers frequently apply high safety coefficients in structural calculations, which can compromise ductility. Therefore, it is crucial not to disregard the importance of ductility in structures, as an overly rigid “battle tank” type structure may not always be the optimal solution. In this study, structural impact tests were performed to verify the behavior of ASTM A36 structural steel weldments with fillet welds produced using GMAW (Gas Metal Arc Welding). The weldments were made using a nominally “pure” nickel electrode AWS ERNi-1. Subsequently, they were subjected to out-of-plane structural impact tests, with loading applied transversely to the weld beads. It should be noted that these tests do not refer to standardized impact tests such as Charpy. The weldments were subjected to structural impact loads involving a bending moment (large lever arm).

The organization of the article is as follows: Initially, a theoretical framework provides a comprehensive review of the results from studies on welded structures subjected to structural impact. Subsequently, a section presents the methods and materials, detailing the base metal, electrodes, equipment, and testing conditions. Next, the results and discussions focus on the impact tests, including a comparison between the experimental findings and theoretical predictions derived from a dynamic equation used to estimate the behavior of the weldment under impact loading. Finally, the paper concludes with the main findings and a list of references related to the research.

II. WELDED STRUCTURES SUBJECT TO STRUCTURAL IMPACT

The response of a welded steel structure to dynamic structural impact loading depends on two main factors: the velocity of the impact and the strain rate. The properties of materials are usually evaluated through tests conducted in quasi-static loading situations, with strain rates typically ranging from 10^{-4} to 10^{-1} s^{-1} . However, in structural steels, the mechanical properties are sensitive to the rate of deformation they experience. Therefore, results obtained from quasi-static tests should not be directly applied to the design of structures subjected to dynamic loads.

Andrade and Machado [2] investigated the behavior of ASTM A36 structural steel beams welded with GMAW under structural impact loading. The study aimed a relation between the actual response of the beams and the results predicted by analytical calculations. Two types of metal profiles, a T-beam and an I-beam, varying in length and thickness, were examined. The electrodes used were AWS ER70S-6 with a diameter of 1.2 mm, possessing mechanical properties match to those of the base metal. The weldments were subjected to structural impact at the center of the beam using a mass of 267 kg (hammer + punch). After conducting the experiments, it was observed that the strain rate sensitivity likely enhances the beam's ability to withstand moments under dynamic loading conditions. In addition, a certain discrepancy was noted between the theoretical values obtained from the equations (which were found to be overestimated) compared to the actual deflection values. This difference may be due to the sensitivity to strain rate, which increases yield stress during deformation. Similar observations were made in previous studies [3, 4].

According to Budynas and Nisbett [5], in situations where weld groups are subjected to shear loads from external forces that do not act on the centroid, these groups can experience both translation and rotation occurring between the parts connected by welding. Figure 1 illustrates a schematic of eccentric external loads on “in-plane” welded joints, where the weld can deform freely along its entire length, and “out-of-plane” joints, where part of the weld is constrained due to direct support between the welded plates. Dawe and Kulak [6] emphasized this distinction in the formulation of the ultimate limit state for the resistance of welded connections, highlighting varying levels of conservatism in Codes and standards, as discussed by Machado [7].

Figure 1. Welds with eccentric loading. Reproduced from [7].

Dal Molin and Machado [8] examined the behavior of structural steel assemblies with fillet welds under torsional, in-plane, quasi-static, and dynamic loads. The assemblies were fabricated as “cantilever beams” using GMAW, employing two filler metals with different tensile strength and ductility limits, i. e.: AWS ER70S-6, considered “matching” (mechanical properties similar to base metals), and AWS ER120S-G, considered “overmatching” (mechanical properties superior to base metals). One weldment featured two weld beads oriented transversely to the “T” loading direction, while another utilized “C” welds. Additionally, another weld bead was placed parallel to the loading direction, connecting them. The base metals employed were ASTM A36 structural steel and SR235 JR carbon-manganese steel. The authors observed a significant influence of preheating on the AWS ER120S-G weldment, resulting in a reduction in hardness of approximately 13% compared to the weldment at ambient temperature. The pre-heating increased the resistance of the weldment with “C” weld beads, allowing it to withstand 11% more loading. Regarding structural impact, the resistance increased by 7% compared to weldments at room temperature. However, the study indicated that the weldments supported less load in the structural impact test compared to the quasi-static test. The analytical model proposed for sizing the weld beads proved effective, predicting lower values than those observed in practical tests, both for the structural impact and quasi-static tests.

Kulmann and Machado [9] evaluated the behavior of welded “I” profiles, with and without reinforcement, under structural impact. The profiles were fabricated from ASTM A36 structural steel and EN 10149-2 S700MC low alloy steel using the GMAW with two different consumables: AWS ER70S-6, considered “matching”, and AWS ER110S-G, considered “overmatching”. The study revealed that “I” profiles made from S700MC steel exhibited less deformation compared to those made from ASTM A36. Regarding mechanical strength, the reinforcements were found to be significant, as the enhanced rigidity of the structure resulted in decreased buckling of the beams.

The behavior of fillet welds subjected to quasi-static and structural impact was analyzed in [10]. Two base metals (ASTM A36 and ASTM A572 Gr50) and two electrodes were used in weldment fabrication: AWS ER70S-6, considered “matching” to structural steels, and AWS ER120S-G, considered “overmatching”. The weldments were manufactured as cantilever beams, with all energy applied to the weld beads. When comparing quasi-static tests with structural impact, the authors observe that weldments withstood most loads under quasi-static conditions, regardless of the electrode or base metal used. AWS ER120S-G weldments that were preheated to 150 °C and subjected to longitudinal loading exhibited greater resistance over shorter durations compared to those subjected to transverse loads under the same conditions. The aim of the authors was to determine the fracture threshold of the weldments. After the tests, it was observed that the energy to reach the threshold was 0.76 kJ for ASTM A572 Gr50 weldments and 0.78 kJ for ASTM A36 weldments. Hoffmann and Machado highlight that the difference between longitudinal and transverse loading conditions was 50% less for ASTM A572 Gr50 weldments with preheating and AWS ER70S-6 electrode, and 46% less for ASTM A36 weldments under the same conditions.

The study conducted by [11] investigated the experimental and numerical analyses of small butt-welded plates exposed to air blast loads, emphasizing the impact of welded joints on the resilience of blast-resistant structures. The evaluation encompassed the primary characteristics of the welded joints, including their shape, properties, and residual stress, which were essential for understanding the effects of blast loading. Macrographs were used to analyze the welded joints geometry. Additionally, mechanical properties were assessed from various regions of the bead of weld. Applying a thermo-mechanical model, the residual stresses due to the welding process were determined. Two numerical methods were used to achieve this: the conventional weapons effects program, known for its cost-benefit-effectiveness but with some limitations, and the arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian method, which provides detailed computational analysis. The aim was to compare the effects of the air blast on the plates. After simulations, the two methods showed to align with the experimental results. Calculations were performed under six distinct conditions to examine how the material properties and residual stresses distribution affect the dynamic response. Permanent deflections were used to verify the load-bearing capacity of the welded joints. Results revealed that bending deformations were facilitated due fields of residual stress.

Huang et al. [12] investigated the behavior of web-opened steel beams (WOSBs) subjected to structural impact tests. For the experiments, 26 specimens were manufactured. The aim of the investigations was to examine several factors, such as mechanical strength, inter-opening space, impact energy, and open height. Results showed shear deformation of Vierendeel and out-of-plane lateral buckling of the web in WOSBs. The delay of time (between the force peaks) was approximately 9.77% of the total duration of the impact occurs in the initial phase. It was found that increased the energy of impact and the height of opening had negative effects on the WOSBs impact resistance. Specifically, as the opening height or energy of impact increased, the average residual displacements for WOSBs H1, H2 and H3 (corresponding from steels of different classes Q235, Q550, and Q690, respectively) increased by 23.85%, 34.05%, and 33.20%, approximately. The efficiency of the average impact was 77.38%, 72.90%, and 72.74% for H1, H2 and H3. These findings suggest that the WOSBs unique geometric characteristics may be adequately utilized in the design of structures needed to absorb energy. Furthermore, the study proposed a methodology for calculating the WOSBs impact resistance performance, including the factor of dynamic amplification and the ratio of energy absorbed as specified by current steel structure design standards.

The collapse resistance of steel-frame structures was investigated by [13]. To this end, the authors modeled a “beam-column” type substructure and analyzed, through structural impact tests using a drop hammer, the effect of a series of scale ratios on the dynamic response of the structure. Two impact tests were conducted, and the results, after comparison, were used for model validation. At the same time, a new detailed model of a double half-span beam-column was proposed to verify the influence of varying impact energy, obtained by varying the mass and impact velocity, on the force generated during impact and the vertical displacement. After conducting the tests, the results were analyzed using the finite element method, where it was observed that the velocity of the hammer at the moment of impact is directly related to the force of that impact. The mass of the drop hammer exhibited effects on the force plateau and the duration of the structural impact. The observed linear (positive) correlation between the impact duration and the maximum vertical displacement with the involved kinetic energy led to the proposal of a new linear fitting model between displacement and impact energy. In structures with a smaller scale ratio, adjustments in impact velocity by varying the height of the drop hammer were necessary to achieve the desired variations in impact energy. At the end of the study, the authors present a scale ratio to predict the collapse resistance behavior of the structure.

The direct impact Hopkinson method was used to simulate the compression of small energy absorbers, as evaluated by [14]. To this end, the authors conducted numerical and experimental analyses of the phenomena involved in this condition. The main focus of the study was to predict in detail the strength of welds obtained through the laser welding process under two distinct loading conditions: quasi-static and structural impacts. The research explored determining factors that may affect the way cracks are distributed in cases of deformation, as well as the potential application of the proposed method in models for predicting failure mechanisms. Two distinct Johnson-Cook models were observed, one being more simplified and the other incorporating Hockett-Shelby extrapolation that includes linear damage dependent on stress triaxiality and Lode angle. The models were calibrated (for the base metal and welds) based on experimental tests at three different strain rates. After validation, the models were subjected to static and dynamic compressive loading. Consistent results were found for the quasi-static tests, with a margin of error of 5%. An increase in strength within the range of 15% was observed in impact tests, with an almost linear increase as a function of impact velocity. When comparing the average plateau forces obtained from the two types of tests (static and dynamic), the authors found a difference of less than 10%, indicating that quasi-static compression tests can be applied to estimate the total absorbed energy.

The behavior of CFDST-K joints through a combination of experimental and nonlinear analysis to assess performance metrics such as the evolution of strain, the capacity degradation, the impact force, the energy absorption capacity, and the bearing capacity degradation was investigated by [15]. The study examined various structure-related parameters, including the rate of hollow and the steel tube thickness. Findings revealed that CFDST-K joints significantly improve impact resistance, promoting a more efficient energy distribution. The optimal hollow rate identified was 0.63. To enhance the anti-

impact properties, the ratio of the diameter to the outer tube thickness should remain below 30. At low impact energies, there was virtually no effect on the inner tube thickness. The authors concluded that the proposed and experimentally validated methods provide a solid basis for the development of more dependable CFDST-K joints for steel structures.

Smolnicki and Sokolski [16] analyzed, based on computational simulations, the stresses in welded joints of support structures for heavy machinery under variable loading conditions. The researchers noted that for each configuration of variation in the analysis, the technical condition of the support nodes was related to the intensity of the deterioration processes. Various positioning conditions of the supports in relation to the machine chassis were evaluated. For the assessment using the finite element method, the hot-spot method was adopted, which is indicated for analyses of highly complex welded structures. The results of the study indicated that both the values and the distribution of von Mises stresses and their respective axial components were significantly influenced by the load value. Depending on the positioning of the body, changes in the sensitivity of the weld due to the impact of the wheel were identified, with the highest values obtained when the wheel was located between the diaphragms of the ring girder. In the lower region of the wheels, the weld experiences compression, while between them, tension occurs. Subsequently, there is a change in the sign of the stress, considerably increasing its amplitude. These reasons led the authors to conclude that the usual von Mises stresses are not suitable for analyzing stresses in their welded supports.

III. METHODS AND MATERIALS

The base metal used in the manufacture of weldments was ASTM A36 structural steel, which is justified by its widespread use in metal structures due to its weldability and relatively high mechanical properties while maintaining good toughness. AWS ERNi-1 was the chosen electrode. This electrode has high ductility compared to steel electrodes and is composed mainly of approximately 96% Ni and 3% Ti. Table 1 shows the base metal chemical composition, determined via optical emission spectrometry in accordance with ASTM A36/A36M-19 [17] standards and the chemical composition of AWS ERNi-1 as per the certificate of conformity issued by the manufacturer, compliant with AWS A5.11/A5.11M:2010 [18]. Table 2 displays the mechanical properties of both the base metal and the electrode, according to the certificates of conformity provided by the manufacturers. Figure 2 presents the base metal micrograph, captured with an optical microscope following surface preparation and etching using a 2% Nital. The microstructure observed is typical of normalized steel, consisting of colonies of pearlite (dark phase) and ferrite- α (light phase).

Table 1. Base metal and electrode chemical composition [% in mass].

Material	Ni	C	Mn	P	S	Si	Cu	Al	Ti	Fe
ASTM A36	-	0.14	1.57	<0.01	<0.01	0.20	0.01	0.033	-	Remainder
AWS ER Ni-1	95.7	0.014	0.409	0.004	0.001	0.46	0.004	0.062	3.08	0.005

Table 2. Base metal and electrode mechanical properties.

Material	Yield Stress [MPa]	Ultimate Tensile Strength [MPa]	Elongation [%]
ASTM A36	250	400 - 550	20
AWS ER Ni-1	330	380	20

The weldments were fabricated using ASTM A36 plates of varying thicknesses: one plate was 31.5 mm thick, designated as the “base plate”, and another was 63.5 mm thick, referred to as the “impact plate” due to its direct contact with the loading hammer during impact. Weldments using AWS ERNi-1 were produced with GMAW and argon as shielding gas. Other conditions maintained constant included welding in the flat position for fillet welding, a 18 mm distance from the contact nozzle to the workpiece, a shielding gas flow rate of 15 l/min, and a neutral working angle. Welding operations were performed using the Yaskawa Motoman Robotics MA 1400 welding robot in conjunction with the Fronius TransPuls Synergic 4000 R power source, ensuring precision and repeatability. Figure 3 shows the weldment dimensions.

Figure 2. Microstructure of base metal ASTM A36.

Figure 3. Weldments dimensions.

The structural impact tests were conducted using equipment developed at the Welding and Related Techniques Laboratory (LS&TC) of the Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (Figure 4). This setup includes an impact hammer (252 kg) and an inclinometer to measure the angle of applied load.

Figure 4. Structural Impact Tests Equipment.

The impact energy values corresponding to different hammer inclinations were determined in previous experimental studies, as detailed by [8]. Table 3 presents the impact velocities and energy values obtained for various launch angles of the hammer during the structural impact tests.

Table 3. Impact velocity and energy at various angles. Adapted from [8].

Hammer angle	15°	30°	45°	60°	75°	90°
Impact velocity [m/s]	1.28	2.49	3.71	4.84	5.83	6.77
Impact energy [kJ]	0.21*	0.78*	1.73 (+/- 0.01)	2.95 (+/- 0.01)	4.28 (+/-0.06)	5.77 (+/- 0.03)

Note: * Deviation from the mean less 0.01 kJ.

Vickers hardness profiles were obtained using a load of 0.5 kgf and an indentation time of 10 seconds along a line transverse to weld bead 1 mm below the surface of the plates. The test followed the standard ASTM E384-22 [19] and covered the base metal, heat-affected zone (HAZ), and weld metal. To compare the experimental results of the transverse displacement of the large arm of the weldment due to impact (w_f) at different impact velocities, Equation (1) from Goldsmith [20] was applied for analytical purposes.

$$w_f = \frac{2v_0L^2}{a^2} \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\phi_i^2} \left[\frac{(\text{sen}\phi_i \cosh\phi_i - \cos\phi_i \sinh\phi_i)(\text{sen}\phi_i + \text{senh}\phi_i)(\cos\phi_i + \cosh\phi_i)}{(\text{sen}\phi_i \cosh\phi_i - \cos\phi_i \sinh\phi_i)^2 + Q \cdot (\text{sen}\phi_i + \text{senh}\phi_i)^2} \right] \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{\cosh\frac{\phi_i x}{L} - \cos\frac{\phi_i x}{L}}{\cosh\phi_i + \cos\phi_i} - \frac{\sinh\frac{\phi_i x}{L} - \text{sen}\frac{\phi_i x}{L}}{\sinh\phi_i + \text{sen}\phi_i} \right] \text{sen} \frac{\phi_i^2 a^2 t}{L^2} \tag{1}$$

where, L is the length of the beam, v_0 is the impact velocity, x refers to the distance from the support to the point of impact on the beam, t is the impact time, the natural frequency of the beam $a^2 = \sqrt{EI/\rho A}$, and $Q = \phi_i \frac{(\text{sen}\phi_i \cosh\phi_i - \cos\phi_i \sinh\phi_i)}{1 + \cos\phi_i + \cosh\phi_i}$, being ϕ_i is the roots of the Equation (1) (Table 4), I the inertia moment, E the modulus of elasticity, A is the cross-sectional area, and ρ the specific mass. The mass ratio $M = m_1/m_2$, where m_1 is the impacted mass (mass of the beam), and m_2 is the impacting mass (which causes the impact).

Table 4. Roots of ϕ_i as a function of the mass ratio. Adapted from Goldsmith [20].

ϕ_i	M					
	< 1/10	1/10	1/2	1	2	> 2
ϕ_1	0.75M	0.731	1.04799	1.19161	1.31965	0.5 π
ϕ_2	1.25 π	3.931	4.03652	4.11972	4.23720	1.5 π
ϕ_3	2.25 π	7.083	7.13400	7.18994	7.28084	2.5 π
ϕ_4	3.25 π	10.220	10.25664	10.29839	10.37041	3.5 π
ϕ_5	4.25 π		13.38770	13.42093	13.48020	4.5 π
ϕ_6	5.25 π		16.52269	16.55021	16.60043	5.5 π
ϕ_7	6.25 π		19.65969	19.68824	19.72671	6.5 π

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The welding parameters listed in Table 5 were derived from instrumented tests using the IMC SAP - V 4.01 data acquisition system. These parameters were optimized to ensure arc stability, minimize spatter, and achieve complete weld bead penetration. A precise balance of these parameters leads to a reduction in defects such as porosity and inclusions [21, 22]. Moreover, the selection of appropriate parameters is essential not only for mechanical performance but also for the aesthetic quality of the weld, as variations can lead to visual defects, which may indicate underlying issues in weld integrity [23].

The structural impact tests were conducted under conditions similar to those described by [10], but using AWS ERNi-1. The test conditions were as follows: ASTM A36 base metal, transverse loading of the weld beads, and welding performed at room temperature. Figure 5 shows the macrograph of the weld bead made with AWS ERNi-1. Figure 6 shows the weldment with AWS ERNi-1 before and after the structural impact test with the loading hammer launched at a 45-degree angle. In 6(b) it is clear to see the displacement of the impacted member relative to the base, as evidenced by the use of a 90-degree square (used as a reference to highlight the permanent displacement of the lever arm).

Table 5. Welding parameters.

Electrode	Average Voltage [V]	Average Current [A]	Wire Feed Speed [m/min]	Welding Speed [mm/s]	Welding Energy* [kJ/mm]
AWS ERNi-1	23.2	260	6.2	4.6	1.3

*Considering 100% of efficiency.

Figure 5. Macrograph of the AWS ERNi-1 weld bead.

Figure 6. Weldment before the test (a) and after the structural impact test with the hammer launched at a 45-degree angle (b).

Table 6 presents the average energy values obtained from impact tests conducted to determine the threshold fracture. Each test was repeated three times for each hammer launch. The table also includes analytical results obtained using Goldsmith's equation for structural impact on a cantilever beam, Equation (1).

Table 6. Results of structural impact tests on AWS ERNi-1 weldments and comparative with analytical.

Hammer Launched Angle [degree]	Impact Velocity [m/s]	Impact Energy [kJ]	Weldment Post-Impact Angle [degree]	Impact Displacement Experimental [mm]	Impact Displacement Equation (1) [mm]	Qualitative Result
30	2.49	0.78	1.20	6.28	10.65	Plastic Deformation
40	3.33	1.41	1.94	10.15	14.24	Plastic Deformation
45	3.71	1.73	2.94	15.18	15.86	Plastic Deformation
50	4.11	2.13	3.20	16.78	17.57	Fracture Threshold
60	4.84	2.95	-	-	-	Complete Fracture

Table 7 shows the comparative results of the energy values required to determine the threshold fracture in the present research and the study conducted by Hoffmann and Machado [10]. The ductility of the AWS ERNi-1 resulted in a significant increase in energy needed to reach the threshold fracture of weld bead 1, approximately 213%. Figure 7 shows the fracture threshold of the AWS

ERNi-1 weld bead evidenced by dye penetrant testing and Figure 8 shows the complete fracture of weld bead 1 with the hammer launched at 60 degrees.

The Goldsmith equation for impacts on cantilever beams is widely used to predict the displacement caused by an impact on metallic structures. However, as pointed out by [20], these equations are based on simplified assumptions that disregard certain real effects, such as material heterogeneities, welding imperfections, and actual boundary conditions during the impact. The discrepancies between the experimental and analytical displacements observed can be attributed to these simplifications. Additionally, the effect of strain hardening (the increase in material strength after plastic deformation) in metallic materials like AWS ERNi-1 may not have been fully accounted for in the theoretical formulation.

Ductile materials tend to absorb more energy during deformation, which explains the 213% increase in the energy required to fracture AWS ERNi-1 compared to AWS ER70S-6 weldments. This property makes these materials excellent options for applications subjected to impacts by allowing greater energy absorption before structural failure. The fracture behavior of metallic materials, especially welds, is influenced by various factors, including microstructure, welding process, and the presence of imperfections such as porosity or cracks [24]. According to [25], fracture mechanics explains that for ductile materials a larger amount of energy is dissipated in plastic deformation before fracture occurs, resulting in a higher fracture threshold. The fact that complete fracture occurred at 60-degree with 2.95 kJ, as shown, reinforces the robustness of AWS ERNi-1 fillet welds under severe impact. This behavior is consistent with elasto-plastic fracture theory, where crack propagation is delayed by the material's ability to deform plastically along the fracture zone. The high strength and ductility characteristics of AWS ERNi-1 indicate its suitability for applications with high dynamic loads. Its performance positions AWS ERNi-1 as an excellent option for structural steel weldments subjected to impact loading; however, it should be carefully evaluated due to the high costs involved.

Table 7. Comparison of impact energy values for threshold fracture of the weld bead.

Research	Electrode	Hammer Launched Angle [degree]	Impact Energy to Reach Fracture Threshold [kJ]
Hoffmann and Machado [10]	AWS ER70S-6	27	0.68
Authors of this paper	AWS ERNi-1	50	2.13

After the impact tests, a hardness test was conducted on the weld beads impacted with a 50-degree load hammer to assess the mechanical strength behavior of the weld bead under structural impact. The hardness results are shown in Table 8, indicating a relative increase in hardness of approximately 93% in the base metal and 42% in the heat-affected zone.

Figure 7. Fracture threshold of the AWS ERNi-1 weld bead evidenced by dye penetrant testing.

Figure 8. Weld bead 1 complete fracture of the AWS ERNi-1 weldments.

The substantial increase in hardness in both the base metal and the HAZ can be attributed to the strain hardening effects induced by the impact loading. According to [26], the mechanical properties of materials, including hardness, can be significantly enhanced through processes such as strain hardening, which occurs when a material is deformed beyond its elastic limit. This phenomenon is crucial in applications where welds are subjected to dynamic loads, as it allows the material to absorb energy without catastrophic failure. The HAZ is particularly sensitive to thermal cycles during the welding process, which can lead to changes in microstructure and mechanical properties. The thermal gradient experienced in the HAZ significantly affects the phase transformations within the microstructure, resulting in varied hardness profiles [27]. Maintaining adequate toughness in this region is critical; otherwise, it may become a weak point in the welded structure, increasing susceptibility to crack formation under stress [28].

Table 8. Results of Vickers hardness of weldment manufactured with AWS ERNi-1.

Test Region	Max. Hardness [HV 0.5] Before Impact	Max. Hardness [HV 0.5] After Impact
Weld Metal	186.7	360.3
HAZ	279.9	395.9

Note: Hammer elevation angle of 50-degrees, corresponding to the threshold fracture.

After conducting the impact tests, an EDX scan was carried out using a scanning electron microscope to examine possible variations in dilution within the cross-section of the weld bead in the weldment fabricated with AWS ERNi-1. The scan ranged from the root of the joint to the face of the weld, following the throat line, in 1 mm increments. No significant differences were observed in the percentages of chemical elements (by weight) during the EDX analysis; thus, the dilution remained practically constant across all regions of the bead, demonstrating its homogeneity.

Table 9 and Figure 9 show the results of the EDX analysis. The consistency in chemical composition throughout the weld bead is critical, as noted by [26]. The authors highlight that uniformity in chemical composition can significantly influence the mechanical properties of welds, including strength and ductility. Variations in dilution can lead to the formation of weak points that may compromise the structural integrity of welded joints. This is particularly relevant in critical applications where material performance under dynamic loading conditions is essential.

The fracture surface obtained after structural impact tests was analyzed (Figure 10). As expected, the surface shows a significant presence of spherical microcavities (dimples) and extensive plastic deformation, characteristics of ductile fracture attributed to the high plastic deformation capacity of the nickel electrode.

The presence of these dimples results from the coalescence of voids formed during plastic deformation, which allows the material to deform significantly before fracture, thus enhancing energy absorption capabilities. Ductile materials, such as nickel, for example, can undergo considerable plastic deformation, which not only contributes to their toughness but also improves resistance to crack propagation [29].

Table 9. Results of EDX for the AWS ERNi-1 weld bead cross-section, presented in [%].

Point Location on the Throat Line	Ni	Fe	Ti	Mn	Si
1 mm from the edge	78.88	17.27	2.72	0.59	0.54
2 mm from the edge	81.36	14.74	2.99	0.59	0.31
2 mm from the root	82.33	13.70	2.93	0.57	0.47
1 mm from the root	83.17	13.04	3.02	0.37	0.40

Figure 9. Spectrum obtained by EDX for the AWS ERNi-1 weld bead cross-section. (a) 1 mm from the edge, (b) 2 mm from the edge, (c) 2 mm from the root, and (d) 1 mm from the root.

Figure 10. Fracture surface of the AWS ERNi-1 weld bead after impact test.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study aimed to verify the behavior of GMAW fillet welds on ASTM A36 steel made with a high ductility electrode AWS ERNi-1 under structural impact tests. After analyzing the results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- For cantilevered beam structures with large lever arms, the high ductility of the electrode proved to be a very positive factor in terms of structural impact, as 213% more energy was needed to reach the threshold fracture of the weldments compared to those tested by Hoffmann and Machado [10];
- The Vickers hardness test showed a significant increase in the mechanical strength of the AWS ERNi-1 weldments after structural impact, reaching values of 93% in the weld metal region and 42% in the HAZ;
- Goldsmith's equation for the analytical solution of cantilever beams subjected to structural impact proved to be effective in estimating transverse displacement, where the most accurate estimate was obtained when the hammer was launched at a 45-degree angle, with a difference between the values of just 4.47%;

- The EDX scan indicated satisfactory homogeneity of the weld beads with AWS ERNi-1, as no significant difference was observed in the percentages of chemical elements present;
- Fracture surface analysis of weld beads using pure nickel electrodes AWS ERNi-1 revealed ductile fracture characteristics, consistent with the high ductility of the filler metal;
- It is important to emphasize here that this paper is not proposing the indiscriminate use of nickel electrodes in welding structural steels, but rather presenting it as a possible solution for special situations involving structural impact.

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